

The feed behind the footprint: average rations for farm animals in Germany

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1 Abstract

Introduction. Agriculture is one of the main drivers of planetary boundary transgression, with animal products in particular playing a major role. Although the production of animal feed accounts for a large share of this impact, there is no data available for Germany on the average feed composition for different farm animals. In order to fill this gap, this study derived data sets for the average feed supply for the most important farm animals (cattle, pigs, poultry).

Method. Material flow analysis (MFA) was used to determine the average feed compositions and quantities for the various farm animals. Average feed compositions were determined on the basis of official statistical data on domestic animal feed consumption and feeding recommendations for the various animal species. These were then discussed with experts and adjusted accordingly.

Results. Based on these statistical data, tables of the average feed composition for the most relevant German farm animals were created.

Discussion. The information on average feed composition supplements existing information and, on this basis, enables more detailed studies of the environmental impact of animal food consumption in Germany and the derivation of strategies for sustainable food systems. In addition, optimisation strategies in feeding and scenarios for future changes in feeding practices can be analysed and evaluated in terms of their environmental impacts.

2 Introduction

Agriculture is one of the main drivers in exceeding planetary boundaries (Campbell et al., 2017). In particular the transgression of the planetary boundaries 'biosphere integrity' and 'biogeochemical flows' is mainly due to agricultural practices (ibid.). But also regarding climate change, agriculture has a significant impact: According to Crippa et al. (2021), food systems account for a third of global greenhouse gas emissions. Food consumption in Germany accounts for 2.060 kg CO₂e of greenhouse gas emissions per person and year (Eberle & Mumm, 2024), which corresponds to 21 per cent of consumption-related greenhouse gas emissions in Germany (Global Carbon Budget, 2024). Other studies conducted in recent years

show similar results for Germany (Eberle & Fels, 2016; Schmidt et al., 2019). In particular, animal products account for high impacts on biodiversity (Eberle & Mumm, 2024) and greenhouse gas emissions from food consumption in Germany (Eberle & Fels, 2016; Eberle & Mumm, 2024; Schmidt et al., 2019).

Some of the greenhouse gas emissions originate from livestock farming itself, for example methane emissions from cattle farming or nitrous oxide emissions from manure storage and treatment (e. g. Chadwick et al., 2011; Petersen et al., 2013; Baral et al., 2018). Another part originates from the production of animal feed. Eberle & Mumm (2024) show that 85 per cent of climate-relevant emissions from animal products (meat and meat products, milk and dairy products) in the German food basket originate in agriculture and 15 per cent in processing, trade and households. Around half of agricultural emissions from animal products are attributable to the provision of feed and the other half to direct emissions from animal husbandry. Animal products are also responsible for the largest share of biodiversity and land use impacts. Animal feed causes 77 percent of the impact on biodiversity; in addition, three-quarters of the land used is for producing animal feed (Eberle & Mumm, 2024).

Despite the significance of feed production for environmental impacts from food, there is a lack of statistical information on the average composition of feed for different animal species in Germany. However, this would be necessary for a more detailed analysis of environmental impacts from food and the optimisation strategies that can be derived from this for feeding practices. To close this gap, data sets for average feed intake were derived in a study on greenhouse gas emissions from food for the Agora Agrar think tank.

3 Methodology

Material flow analysis (MFA) was chosen as the method to determine the average feed compositions and quantities for the various animal species based on national feed consumption (Graedel, 2019). Total feed supply was determined from national feed statistics (BMEL, 2024). To compensate for annual fluctuations, the average of the last three financial years (2020/21 to 2022/23) was used as a basis. Only feed items relevant in terms of mass were taken into account, covering more than 95 % of total feed use.

To allocate feed supply to livestock production, average German animal husbandry systems were determined based on recommendations of the Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft (KTBL, 2024). The datasets provide average values for typical German animal husbandry systems, including product outputs (e. g. slaughter weight, milk yield, number of calves), number of young animals and feed intake. In the KTBL dataset, some data are reported per year, others per production cycle. To harmonize the data reference, all data were converted to a yearly basis. Mortality rates are already accounted for in the KTBL data. The KTBL datasets also provide economic values for the outputs, which were used for economic allocation between co-products (e. g. milk, meat, manure). Datasets were selected based on the following parameters:

- **Performance level** – Three performance levels are distinguished in the KTBL datasets: *low*, *medium*, and *high*, representing increasing levels of production efficiency in animal husbandry systems (i.e. higher output to input ratio with higher total input). In this study, the *high* performance level was selected as the default, reflecting the predominance of high-efficiency production systems in Germany. An exception was

made for conventional Holstein-Friesian dairy cows, for which the *medium* level was applied to align with the national average milk yield of approximately 8,500 kg per cow per year [*high* performance level showed 10,000 kg milk per cow per year]

- **Housing system** – Both conventional and organic production systems were represented according to their respective shares in German animal husbandry. Within each production type, no significant differences were identified in the relevant technical parameters across different housing systems.
- **Breed** – Information on breed was included only where available in the KTBL datasets (i.e. dairy cows, calves, heifers, beef cattle, and laying hens). In these cases, the breed distribution in Germany was taken into account to derive representative average values.

Based on these selections, average German animal husbandry management practices (or unit processes) were defined for:

- **Cattle:** calf rearing, breeding heifers, young bull and heifer fattening, dairy cow and suckler cow husbandry
- **Pigs:** sow husbandry, piglet rearing, pig fattening
- **Poultry:** pullet rearing, laying hen husbandry, broiler and turkey fattening

Plausibility within the datasets (i.e. the relationship between inputs and outputs) is assumed, based on the fact that the recommendations are based on combined real-life data and knowledge of German farmers. Plausibility of the calculated production levels (i.e. output per animal place per year) of the KTBL-derived datasets was checked by calculating the number of animals that would be needed in Germany to match domestic production statistics of animal products like milk, meat and eggs. This was done by comparing the production output to the actual number of heads. The domestic animal production statistics and number of animals were taken from Destatis (2024), averaged over the last three financial years (2020/21 to 2022/23). While the figures for milk and pork production processes corresponded well, this was less the case for rearing processes. Since trade in young animals was not taken into account in this simplified model, the figures for young animals were therefore taken from official statistics rather than from the modelled values.

Total feed supply for Germany = domestic feed production - exports + imports

Average German animal husbandry system based on KTBL

Figure 1: Methodological approach

The KTBL data distinguish between forages (e. g. meadow grass, maize silage) and compound feeds (e. g. concentrates for dairy cattle, pullet rearing feed). Forages could be directly mapped to the feed supply statistics. For compound feeds, where KTBL does not specify ingredient compositions, average compound feed formulas were modelled. As a basis, the most relevant feed ingredients by mass were taken from German feed balance and feed-protein balance sheets (BMEL, 2024). The ingredients and their share of the total marketable feedstuff consumption are: Soft wheat (19 %), maize grain (15 %), soybeans (15 %), rapeseed (11 %), barley (8 %), cereal bran (6 %), rye (5 %), and triticale (5 %), representing in total about 83 % of the total marketable feedstuff consumption.

Expert judgement¹ was used to define plausible average compositions of compound feeds for each animal species and production stage. The resulting feed compositions were evaluated using nutrient tables from the Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft (LfL, 2024) to verify dry matter intake and crude protein content. Compound feed formulas were iteratively adjusted until both (i) plausibility of composition and (ii) plausibility of nutrient uptake were achieved.

The modelled feed demand (right side in Figure 1; calculated using equation (1)) was compared to the total feed supply from BMEL. The total demand for each primary feedstuff *i* was calculated as the sum of all direct and indirect feed requirements across the *n* animal unit processes, scaled by the number of animals represented in each process. The calculation followed equation (1):

¹ For this purpose, German experts in the field of poultry, pig and cattle husbandry have been consulted being representatives of science, administration and economics, e.g. feed providers.

$$D_i = \sum_{j=1}^n h_j * \left(a_{i,j} + \sum_{k=1}^m b_{j,k} * s_{i,k} \right) \quad (1)$$

D_i : total demand for primary feedstuff i ,
 h_j : number of animal places or average heads for each animal unit process,
 $a_{i,j}$: direct feed requirement of process j for feedstuff i per animal and year,
 $b_{j,k}$: demand of process j for compound feed k per animal and year, and
 $s_{i,k}$: mass share of primary feedstuff i in compound feed k .

The first term in parentheses represents the direct consumption of feedstuff i by process j , while the second term expands the use of compound feeds into their respective primary feed components. Multiplying by h_j scales the per-animal feed requirements to the total demand per animal category.

The model results matched the supply tables within $\pm 10\%$ for compound feeds and maize silage. For grass-based forages (grass silage, fresh grass), modelled values were 40 – 80 % lower. To close this gap, grass forage quantities were scaled to match the BMEL feed supply tables exactly. This adjustment is considered acceptable, as differences may arise from different water contents or estimation approaches (e. g. pasture intake). Since grass forages have a lower dry matter content, this scaling did not distort overall dry matter or nutrient intake beyond reasonable bounds.

4 Results

In the following, the results for the average feed consumption per animal in Germany are presented. Figure 2 shows the material flows of feed consumption in Germany for the assessed forages and direct feedstuff (i. e. soft wheat).

Figure 2: Supply of forages and direct feedstuff in Germany [in kt]

In Figure 3, the material flows of feedstuff to the compound feeds and their subsequent consumption by the animal husbandry systems are shown.

Figure 3: Supply of compound feeds in Germany [in kt]

The feed data per animal and year was also converted into feed consumption per kg of product (e. g. kilogram meat or kilogram milk), where applicable, to facilitate application in calculating the environmental impact of German food consumption in life cycle assessment (LCA).

In the accompanying excel file seven tables are provided:

- [Feed input per animal and year]: feed input (forages and compound feeds) per animal and year
- [Compound feed composition]: composition of all used compound feeds
- [Feedstuff per animal]: feedstuff intake per animal and year
- [Feedstuff per product]: feedstuff intake per product (e.g. per kilogram liveweight or per egg)
- [Annual compound feedstuff supply]: three year average supply values for feedstuffs used in compound feeds
- [Annual direct feedstuff supply]: three year average supply values for direct feedstuffs
- [Annual compound supply]: three year average supply of compound feeds

5 Discussion

The data on the average feed composition of various farm animals enables more detailed studies on the environmental impact of animal-based foods or animal husbandry in Germany. The average data can also be used to calculate a benchmark for comparing different animal husbandry systems and their respective products for the three most important farm animals in Germany: cattle for milk and meat production, pigs for meat production, and poultry for egg and meat production. Based on this data, optimisation strategies in feeding can be analysed and evaluated in terms of their environmental impact compared to the German average.

In addition, scenarios for future changes in feeding practices can also be analysed in terms of their impact on climate change or biodiversity, for example, in order to derive agricultural policy measures, among other things. Last but not least, these data fill a gap in the comprehensive analysis of greenhouse gas emissions from livestock farming in Germany. In national emissions reporting, emissions from livestock farming include direct emissions, while emissions resulting from the cultivation of the necessary feed are attributed to crop production. This is appropriate in view of the objectives of the emissions inventories and complies with international standards. However, against the backdrop of the discussion on sustainable food systems and the role that animal products play in this, it is equally important to be able to allocate national feed consumption to animal husbandry and the respective animal products. The available data thus supplements existing information and, on this basis, enables strategies for sustainable food systems to be derived.

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7 Literature

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